

Infrared Spectra of π - π Molecular Complexes

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Manuscript received 14 March 1985, accepted 30 October 1986

The infrared spectra of π - π molecular complexes of aromatic hydrocarbons with tetrahalo-*p*-benzoquinones were investigated. The spectra show a new band at 470 cm^{-1} which may be associated with the overtone of the inter-molecular stretching vibrations of the donor and acceptor molecules.

THE geometrical configuration of the π - π molecular complexes both in solid state and in solution has been of considerable interest recently. The utilisation of infrared spectral studies in evaluating the geometrical configuration of benzene-halogen molecular complexes were quite interesting¹. Although the configuration of these π - σ molecular complexes in the solid was established by X-ray diffraction studies^{2,3}, still new informations were obtained from infrared studies. X-ray studies on π - π molecular complexes are rather inadequate. The crystal structure of anthracene-trinitrobenzene⁴ indicates that there are eight molecules (four complexes) per unit cell and the molecules are stacked alternately in columns parallel to the C-axis, but tilted by about 6° from the perpendicular to that axis.

Recently, the crystal structures of chrysene-7,7,8,8-tetracyanoquinodimethane⁵, chrysene-fluoranil⁷ and perylene-fluoranil⁸ indicate overlapping of the donor and acceptor molecules in the neighbouring stacks to be an important factor determining the high photoconduction efficiency of these complexes⁷. However, the X-ray studies on the crystal structures of aromatic hydrocarbons and tetrahalo-*p*-benzoquinones were not very compressive. As the crystals suffer massive damage under X-ray irradiation, Wissenberg photographs could not be taken for a complex crystal structure analysis. Information from oscillating photography shows that the donor and acceptor molecules are not in perfect alignment but rather tilted from C-axis.

In order to get further informations about the geometry of these types of complexes, infrared studies of the molecular complexes of the aromatic hydrocarbons (naphthalene, anthracene, phenanthrene, pyrene and chrysene) with tetrahalo-*p*-benzoquinones (chloranil, bromanil and iodanyl) were performed. In this paper, we are reporting the data of such observations.

Experimental

The chloranil complexes were prepared from hydrocarbons and chloranil supplied by E. Merck.

The compounds were purified from repeated recrystallisation from spectroscopically pure chloroform and by chromatographic adsorption on silica gel. The chloroform used was thoroughly dried and freshly distilled before use. Bromanil and iodanyl were prepared from chloranil by standard methods available in literature. For the crystals of the molecular complexes, the hydrocarbons and the tetrahalo-*p*-benzoquinones were mixed in equimolar proportion in chloroform solution. The solution was slowly evaporated when complex separated out in needle shaped crystals long before the separation of the constituents.

The infrared spectra of the complexes as well as of the hydrocarbons and tetrahalo-*p*-benzoquinones were taken using a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer with normal slit programmes. The spectra were taken using nujol technique with a total scan times of 12 min and scanned upto 200 cm^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

All these complexes show fundamentals which are characteristics of both the donors and acceptors. At least four fundamental vibrations in the range 500-800, 850-950, 1250-1400 and 1650-1750 cm^{-1} are exhibited by the complexes. For the systems under discussion, these vibrations are the ν_s ph (ring) ν_{C-C} , ν_{C-X} ($X=Cl, Br, I$) and ν_{C-O} . Another new band (Fig. 1) arises near 470 cm^{-1} (in chloranil-anthracene complex, 450 $\text{cm}^{-1} = 3 \times 150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) which may involve change in the anthracene-chloranil inter-molecular distance. It may be noted that a band near 110-150 cm^{-1} is associated with inter-molecular stretching vibration for these systems while crystal spectra of these complexes were studied previously⁹. However, this band appears as overtone in all of the complexes studied here. Unfortunately, because of the instrumental limitations, we can not isolate the fundamental in these infrared studies as we cannot go below 200 cm^{-1} . The bands near 500-800 cm^{-1} are associated with ν_{C-X} ($X=Cl, Br, \text{ or } I$), the bands in the region 900-1200 cm^{-1} may be associated with ν_s ph (ring), the bands near 1280-1600

Fig. 1. Ir spectra of (a) anthracene, (b) chloranil and (c) anthracene—chloranil complex.

cm^{-1} may be associated with $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{H}}$, and that at 1685 cm^{-1} (range $1680-1740\text{ cm}^{-1}$) may be associated with $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}^{10}}$. It may be noted that the assignments of the band frequencies could have been more precise if normal coordinate analysis could be done on these molecules. Unfortunately, no normal coordinate analysis has ever been done on such complicated molecular complexes upto now.

The potassium salts of *p*-chloranil absorb at 1524 , 1540 , and 147 cm^{-1} (similarly for bromanil and iodanyl ions)^{11,12}. Absence of the bands around 1524 , 1540 and 147 cm^{-1} in chloranil complexes indicate that the complexes are not ionic but neutral in the ground state. The only new band shown is

the overtones of the inter-molecular stretching frequency at $110-150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (as reported previously)⁹. So we may conclude that these are $\pi-\pi$ molecular complexes. The appearance of inter-molecular vibration (crystal modes) in the spectra of crystals is not uncommon, and is to be expected in the present case where such vibrations may have a marked effect on the charge-transfer band between two molecules. It may be noted that the vibrations which bring about changes both in the ionisation energies of the donor and the electro-affinities of the acceptors may appear in the vibrational spectra of such molecular complexes. These are in accord with the crystal structure data, where it was shown that the complexes are stacked in alternate columns with no change of other inter-molecular distances⁹.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the assistance offered from I.A.C.S., Calcutta, for the infrared data. One of the authors (S.K.) wishes to thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance as Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. R. FOSTER, "Organic Charge Transfer Complexes", Academic, New York, 1969, p. 94.
2. O. HASSEL and K. D. STROMME, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1958, **12**, 1146.
3. O. HASSEL and K. O. STROMME, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1959, **13**, 1781.
4. O. HASSEL and O. ROMMING, *Quart. Rev.*, 1962, **16**, 1.
5. S. O. WALLWORK, *Acta Crystallogr. Comb.*, 1954, **7**, 648.
6. P. J. MUNNOCH and J. D. WRIGHT, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1974, 1897.
7. P. J. MUNNOCH, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1975, 1071.
8. V. M. VINCENT and J. D. WRIGHT, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1974, 70.
9. A. K. DAS and R. BASU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 845.
10. N. B. COLTHUP and D. H. LAWRENCE, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, 1964, pp. 243, 323, 325.
11. Y. IIDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1970, **43**, 345.
12. Y. MATSUNAGA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, **41**, 1609.